

A system of indicators for evaluating public broadcasting corporations

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Abstract. We describe an operational procedure to build an integrated information system (IIS) for monitoring and evaluating the performance of public broadcasting corporations (PBC). The procedure grounds in a conceptual framework derived from evaluation models, and consists of two stages. The first stage is the selection, through expert judgment, of simple indicators that illustrate the most relevant aspects of the corporations. The second stage is the definition of a system of indicators related to each level of the hierarchy of objectives planned by the corporations. The system of indicators has two levels. The first level is a basic indicator system that allows description and monitoring of the reality of the activities of a corporation on a daily basis. The second level consists of a strategic indicator system, which expresses the consequences that the activities of a PBC generate in its environment, both as short-term effects and as medium and long-term impacts.

Keywords: Information system, indicators, evaluation, public broadcasting corporations.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, the public media in European countries are striving not only to adapt to the ongoing technological changes motivated by the development of new digital environments, but also to improve the quality of their public service performance to cope with people's evolving demands. In this sense, the EU considers public broadcasting entities as "an essential element in the quality of the democratic process."¹ The question is reflected in strategic documents and memoranda of most European public radio and television entities. For example, the 'Specifications' document of France Télévisions states that "public service television is meant to be the benchmark for quality and innovation of programs, respect for human rights, pluralism and democratic debate, social inclusion and citizenship, and promotion of the French language"². In a similar line, RTÉ, in the new Five Year Strategy document, states that "Ireland needs strong, independent public service media more than ever. Stabilising RTÉ will contribute in no small way to strengthening and enhancing Irish public life"³.

¹ Amsterdam Protocol on Public Service Broadcasting, 17 June 1997.

² Specifications of France Télévisions, decree 2009-796, 23 June 2009.

³ RTÉ, Strategy 2012-2017.

In order to provide a high quality public service and to adapt to technological evolution and people's demands, public broadcasting corporations need to guarantee their financial sustainability, on the one hand, while striving to maintain or increase the audience shares, on the other hand. At the same time, and because of their public service nature, the corporations should remain accessible and accountable to society as a whole. For those reasons, among other, a public broadcasting corporation needs to be managed with due levels of transparency and accountability in its governance and decision-making processes. In this context, it is crucial to establish reliable information systems that provide all the relevant data to help the management staff in decision-making processes in diverse operational areas and at diverse levels of responsibility.

Undoubtedly, information systems permeate almost every aspect of people's lives today. However, there is a consensus among information specialists about the increasing complexity to draw a line around one specific application system to allow its management and control, considering that the relevant data are collected and distributed on a heterogeneous variety of information sources, most often autonomous, which may deter the exchange of information among them (Hasselbring, 2000).

Particularly, we understand the idea of information system in a practical way, as a set of build-in components that work together to collect, store and process data, and to deliver the resulting pieces of information in an organized, structured, adequate and valuable way for a variety of potential stakeholders. According to the previous arguments, and with the objective to create an informational device to facilitate monitoring and evaluation of the performance of public media, the integrated information system we propose is designed and build up as to cover at least five key dimensions: value of public service, quality, innovation, financing, accountability and governance.

However, it is important to note that there is a conflict between the goals of the professionals building information systems and those of the professionals that will manage them, since the later focus mainly on the collection of information and their classification, as well as on the elaboration of search strategies for its recovery. The conflict has promoted a vision of the use of information from the perspective of the system itself that most often leaves aside the problems of the potential users, which should be never forgotten (Kuhlthau, 1991).

After this introduction, the chapter is structured as follows. Section two describes the foundations and main characteristics of the Delphi technique proposed to obtain consistent input from a panel of experts about the potential of simple indicators to monitor and evaluate performance of public broadcasting corporations and we discuss the operational procedure for the selection of a set of simple indicators from those collected in one or more catalogs proposed by organizations such as M.A.R.S., Media Ethics, Media Act, Media Accountability, Media Sustainability (MSI), or UNESCO. The selection should illustrate accurately the most relevant aspects of the activities carried out by public broadcasting corporations and the characteristics of the contexts within which they operate. In section three we describe and discuss how to elaborate an operational two-layer system of indicators tailored to the informational needs of diverse types of decision-makers in public broadcasting corporations. Finally, section four summarizes our proposal and concludes.

2 The Delphi technique

The Delphi technique began to be used in the middle of XXth century, as an instrument to induce consensus from divergent experts' opinions about a variety of forecasting issues linked to the operations of The Rand Corporation. The first investigations were implemented by Dalkey and Helmer (1963) in the form of expert consultations in several rounds, to facilitate a consensus from the views of a group of experts in particular areas of knowledge. In order to control the opinions, several questionnaires were passed to each expert in an individualized manner, so no meetings were necessary, avoiding face-to-face confrontations of the individuals involved in the process. With this technique, the researcher can interview, or pass a written questionnaire, to a number of experts in a chosen field without having to match them in time or space. In this way, the anonymity of the experts to each other is guaranteed, so it is not possible to condition others' opinions, eliminating the potential bias that could occur if there were personal contact among them (Landeta, 1999).

Linstone and Murray (1975) describe the Delphi technique as “a method for structuring a group communication process so that the process is effective in allowing a group of individuals, as a whole, to deal with a complex problem.” The method is described as a systematic procedure that allows to obtain consensual information from the individual query; most often, the consensual information is expressed in qualitative terms. From the experts' assessments about one or more issues of interest, researchers may draw the corresponding conclusions after statistical treatment of the experts' responses. To carry out the analyses, the group of experts is consulted at least twice on each element or issue of interests. The opinions gathered in the first round are statistically summarized and offered as additional input to the experts for the second round, which may cause them to change their initial assessment, or to ratify their initial scores. The process of successive rounds ends when an acceptable degree of consensus about the issues object of consultation.

2.1 Characteristics and phases

Among the most important features of Delphi method that have an influence on the quality of the results, we can mention (Linstone, Turoff, 1975; Landeta, 1999, 2006; Loo, 2002; Coll et al. 2012, 2013):

- Selection of experts. It is about choosing experts that are able, as a group, to contribute knowledge to represent all the aspects of the problem to be analyzed.
- Anonymity of participants. To eliminate the bias that may occur from personal contact, no expert should know who the other members of the panel are or, at least, the individual answers they provide.
- Iteration process. Researchers pass questionnaires more than once, or pass different questionnaires, to each expert in the panel. At the end of each phase, they offer the ratings added to the panel of experts.
- Controlled feedback. With the information of the previous phase, the experts can maintain or modify their opinions.

- Group statistical response. All responses are taken into account for the preparation of the final report. Questions are formulated in ways that facilitate statistical treatment of the data obtained from the answers.

Our proposal for implementation of the Delphi technique is structured in the following three phases (AECID, 2009):

Initial phase. In this first phase, researchers focus the study on planning. The problem or process object of the research is clearly defined. In our case, the problem is which indicators to select, from the set of proposed public TV indicators, to provide data for our information system. First, the team that is responsible for coordination and supervision is formed; the context in which it is to be performed, is established and the panel of experts is selected. To be successful in this type of studies it is crucial to select adequately the experts or evaluators (Gordon, 1994). Since the panel of experts evaluates qualitatively or quantitatively the indicators, the results obtained in the Delphi depend on the knowledge and the implication of the panel, that is to say, the success of the Delphi depends to a great extent on the quality of the experts.

Exploratory phase. This phase includes the preparation of the questionnaires, completion and compilation of the data of the different rounds of consultation, analysis of the results of each phase, feedback and adjustments until the responses of the experts stabilize. In general, the method allows several rounds to be performed. Loo (2002) argues that the researchers should launch new rounds until the consensus is reached or, alternatively, when the results are repetitive in two successive rounds. Although three to four rounds are typically used, often it is sufficient to perform only two rounds, since the most important changes occur between the first and second rounds (Zolingen and Klaasen, 2003; Hanafin et al., 2007). The diagram in Figure 1 shows the iterative nature of the exploratory phase.

Fig. 1. Exploratory phase. Adapted from AECID, 2009.

Final phase. This phase is dedicated to the analysis of the data obtained and to the elaboration of a final report which includes the conclusions of the process.

In general terms, the steps in which the Delphi technique is developed, including the three phases are:

1. Design of the initial questionnaire by the researchers.
2. Selection of the group of experts covering all the areas included in the study.
3. Experts' response to the first round of questionnaires.
4. Analysis of the results of the first round by the researchers.
5. Sending the aggregate results that were obtained in the first round, and sending the second round of the questionnaire. The experts can maintain their scores or modify them based on the results of the first round.
6. Analysis of the results obtained in the second round. If the level of consensus is too low to be acceptable, new rounds can be launched to achieve a satisfactory result.
7. Once the adequate level consensus has been reached on the objectives of the research, the emerging selection of simple indicators will provide input data for the construction of synthetic indicators related to each one of the strategic areas.

2.2 Evaluation of the quality of the results

The Delphi method provides valuable results when researchers think that only expert judgment can shed light on a particular research topic. This is one of the reasons why it was widely accepted and extended its use. With the application of this method it is possible to reduce the effects that experts with dominant personalities may have on group opinions, relevant information provides feedback at every step, and statistical results can be obtained quickly. However, applying the Delphi method is a complex matter and presents, among other, some weaknesses such as the fact that results would always depend on the choice of experts, i.e. who is part of the study and what prejudices he or she may have; the impunity of possible irresponsible actions on the part of the experts due to anonymity; the manipulation that can be done by the people doing the study; the large amount of time needed to complete the different rounds; and the difficulty of checking the accuracy and reliability of the method in particular situations. In addition, applying Delphi can lead to problems if the experts are not rigorously selected, it may also happen that having to fill in the questionnaires in different rounds, as is a long time, the experts leave without completing the study; or that the researchers do not perform rigorous analysis of the results obtained. To avoid weaknesses, therefore, experts should be well selected to value correctly; researchers have to be cautious with the questions that are asked in the questionnaires avoiding the ambiguity and asking closed questions, and rigorous data analysis has to be done (Landeta 2006; Gordon 1994).

It is also appropriate to consider the number of experts who will participate in each strategic area, since there is no consensus on how many people have to be part of the study. The number of experts will depend, among other things, on the complexity of the problem and the heterogeneity of the indicators to be evaluated, but according to

the literature the minimum is about seven experts per issue (Dalkey, Brown, and Cochran 1969; Wilhelm 2001; Landeta 1999). What needs to be ensured is a diversity of experts that guarantees the quality of the process even in the case that the incidence of dropouts during the consultation is significant (Hallowell and Gambatese 2010).

2.3 Selection of simple indicators for public broadcasting corporations using the Delphi method

We propose the application of the Delphi method to gather the opinions of a group of experts on the current situation of public broadcasting companies in terms of governance, financing, accountability, innovation, quality and public service value. More precisely, we propose to use those opinions to evaluate existing simple indicators compiled in different catalogs, and to select those that would fuel the construction of composite indicators tailored to evaluate the advances of public broadcasting corporations towards their planned objectives.

In this case, to apply the Delphi method the actions shown in Figure 2 must be followed and they are developed as follows:

Fig. 2. Delphi Implementation

Presentation of the project and selection of initial indicators. In our case, the purpose is to generate knowledge base to illustrate the situation of European broadcasting companies regarding each one of the strategic areas under analysis from simple indicators available in catalogs. For the initial listing design, catalogs as M.A.R.S, Media Ethics, Media Act, Media Accountability, Media Sustainability (MSI), and UNESCO, can be consulted. The advantage of working with a list of indicators for each strategic area is that the selection of experts can achieve a greater specificity. In addition, shorter, area-specific questionnaires may prevent the experts from leaving before the process is finished.

Design of the questionnaires. The questionnaires should provide all the information necessary for the experts to know the objectives of the study and how many rounds of consultation are initially planned. Questionnaires must be well structured and clearly worded. We recommend multiple choice questions, while open-answer questions must be avoided. The use of a single measurement scale for the answers would make much easier for the experts the task to fill in all the questions. Many studies use the Likert scales to rank the opinions of the experts about the characteristics of simple indicators regarding operational criteria such as relevance, specificity, and feasibility.

Selection of panel of experts. One of the keys to the success of the Delphi method is the adequate selection of the people who are going to participate in the assessment of the indicators (Landeta, 2006). Individually, they must be able to assess the totality of the indicators related to at least one strategic area. As a panel, the group of experts must be able to provide the researchers with sufficient knowledge and experience to achieve the purpose of the consultation, which is to select the best set of simple indicators to provide data about the reality of public broadcasting corporations. Another practical issue is what can be done to prevent dropouts among experts before the consultation is completed.

Regarding the number of experts who are going to participate in each strategic area, our proposal is to consider a minimum of eight experts per area under the premise that the consultation uses structured questionnaires. Although in absolute terms the minimum number of experts in the panel is about 40, for each strategic area the panel size is within the recommendations made by Okoly and Pawlowski (2004).

First round of completion of the questionnaires. An online survey can be proposed in which the expert person can only access with a user name and a personal password. The implementation of online questionnaires has the advantage that the experts can answer the questions at their convenience from his home or office without having to move. An individualized follow-up may be useful to increase the pace in the collection of data, and to reduce the cost time of processing of the information; additionally, the use of kind reminders guarantees a high response rate.

Data Analysis. The use of statistical techniques allows researchers to describe the assessment of experts in the first phase of consultation. Dimension-reduction multivariate techniques generate the feedback information to be reported to the experts along with the next round of consultation. The feedback report can help the experts in the panel to change or to confirm their previous answers in the next round to achieve a certain degree of informed consensus.

Second round of completion of questionnaires. At the beginning of the second round an individualized report is sent to each expert who participated, containing the global results obtained in the first round. At the same time, the questionnaire is made available to fill in it again, taking into account that now the experts know the statistical results of the previous round.

Data Analysis. A new statistical analysis of the responses from every strategic area is performed again, using the same techniques as in the first round. Once the analyses

have been carried out, the researchers re-examine the scores given by the experts to evaluate the degree of consensus among them. If the objective has been achieved, the final results will be presented, otherwise a new round would be carried out and the process repeated until an acceptable degree of consensus is achieved.

Delphi Results. After analyzing the data collected in the final round, the information obtained will serve to select the list of simple indicators for each area that will be used in the design and construction of composite indicators related to the hierarchy of objectives stated in the strategic plans of diverse public broadcasting corporations.

3 Building a two-layer system of composite indicators

This section contains an operational procedure to generate a system of indicators oriented to support monitoring and evaluation of the performance of public broadcasting corporations according to their own strategic plans. Strategic Planning can be understood as a systematic process for developing and implementing actions to achieve corporate goals or objectives. Ideally, every organization should have a strategic plan that guides their activities in function of their objectives. For companies or corporations, the strategic plan guides and provides a general direction for their projects and activities over time.

A system of indicators could be seen as a tool oriented both to support the processes of planning and decision making and to monitor and evaluate activities, projects and policies. The design of a complete system of indicators for any entity, in our case public broadcasting corporations, first needs a clear definition of the priority objectives and strategic areas. Obviously, the priority objectives will be, in general, specific for each organization because they respond to the reality and rationale of each particular corporation. On the contrary, the strategic areas would be considered common for all the corporations targeted; specifically, five strategic areas will be considered: governance, financing, accountability, innovation, quality and value.

The cross-intersection between the five strategic areas and the set of priority objectives, contingent for each corporation, defines a matrix of order 5 by N (where N is the number of specific objectives for a given corporation) that must be covered and monitored by the system of indicators proposed.

The system of indicators for monitoring and evaluation of corporate performance should be based on the nature of the information available to diverse types of decision-makers and involves the definition of suitable operational indexes for selecting a structured set containing the most valuable simple indicators.

3.1 Theoretical framework

The system of indicators will be structured following a theoretical framework resulting from the integration of two well-known corporate evaluation models: (i) the Logical Framework Analysis (LFA) and (ii) the CIPP evaluation model.

The Logical Framework Analysis (Sartorius, 1991; Bakewell and Garbutt, 2005) is a tool used in the context of objective planning that allows presenting, in a logical and systematic way, the hierarchy of objectives of an entity and its causal relationships. The LFA allows the evaluation of the results according to the degree of fulfillment of the previously planned objectives.

The CIPP evaluation model (Worthen and Sanders, 1987; Stufellbeam and Shinkfield, 2002) understands evaluation as a process designed to generate information that allows decision-makers to evaluate the different alternatives available during the implementation of different processes and actions.

The combination of LFA and CIIP defines the indicator system into two layers or subsystems: The basic system and strategic system. The basic system is oriented towards short-term planning and daily management, and will be composed of indicators linked to the monitoring of the evolution of resources, processes and products, while the strategic system focuses specifically on the effects of the activities and on the permanent impacts generated through them; that is, it is oriented to strategic planning in the medium and long term.

The indicators that conform the basic system are usually indicators focused on a single aspect to be measured related to short-term operational issues. The indicators of the strategic system can also be partial indicators, but since their objective is to offer information on aspects of reality with multiple dimensions (effects and impacts), they are most often composite indicators that reflect in an aggregated way the different dimensions to be monitored and evaluated.

3.2 From the Delphi selection of indicators to the information set of the system

The second step towards the definition and construction of a system of indicators for public television corporations begins after Delphi is completed. The results provided by the experts about the suitability of simple indicators provide the guidelines that will feed and inform the analytical methods applied later on; that is, the Delphi final results must be processed and analyzed with the purpose of generating a final list of simple indicators, or information set, that will eventually be used to compose the system of indicators.

This process of selection and prioritization of the partial indicators will be based on three principles or instruments: (i) the definition of synthetic indexes of relative operability for each partial indicator (ii) the typology of the indicators (resource, process, product, effect and impact), and (iii) the choice of feasibility thresholds for each priority action.

The scores provided by the experts who participated in Delphi in three key characteristics, relevance, efficacy and feasibility, will be processed using multivariate statistical techniques to construct for each individual indicator a compound operating index with the objective to select the final set of partial indicators. It seems obvious that indicators with higher values in the operability index should be more likely to be selected and be part of the indicator system, but it seems also reasonable to introduce additional criteria in the selection process to avoid potential deficiencies. In particular, it should be avoided that any relevant aspect of the corporation ceases to be monitored, it will be imposed that all crosses between strategic areas and priority objectives must

have at least an adequate number of indicators, with a minimum number of two. For that reason, the selection of indicators is carried out by establishing a minimum value or threshold of feasibility, different by priority action, which delimits which indicators are the most feasible according to experts' judgement.

This selection methodology should provide the final set of partial indicators that cover in a balanced way each dimension of the cross-matrix of key strategic areas and priority actions. This final list of partial indicators is the starting point for the next stage of the proposal, where the information contained in the partial indicators will be aggregated in a reduced set of synthetic indexes that will serve to monitor governance, financing, accountability, innovation, quality and public service value of public audiovisual corporations in the new digital era.

3.3. From simple indicators to composite indexes

The ultimate objective of a complete system of indicators is to have reliable and truthful information about the entity or object to be monitored. Having a comprehensive system of indicators that enables and facilitates the evaluation and favors the adaptation of the activity of a public body to its assigned objectives, in theory, allows the managers to optimize effectiveness and the level of efficiency in the use of the public resources; but, potentially, due to the possible multiplicity of partial indicators to report on the same or related aspects about the evolution of the corporation, it would be possible that the information provided for two partial indicators would be contradictory, and therefore, it seems convenient to equip the System of Indicators with a set of composite or synthetic indicators that enable and favor a rapid and complete understanding of the evolution of the organization and the degree of fulfillment of its objectives.

According to Hammond (1995), a composite indicator is a construct that provides a clue to a matter of larger significance or makes perceptible a trend or phenomenon that is not immediately detectable. We can think that the main objective of a composite indicator is to summarize in a single measure the information of a set of related simple indicators, facilitating in this way the understanding of the subject being analyzed. The principal advantages of synthetic index are that they can simplify the interpretation of complex topics, facilitate the evaluation of policies and programs, as well as accountability, and allow comparison between units of analysis and over time.

The use of composite indicators is nowadays generalized (Saisana and Tarantola, 2002) but it also hides potential drawbacks, because reducing and synthesizing a set of indicators may simplify the interpretation of results, but can also give a wrong message if they have deficiencies in his definition and construction. Furthermore, the information and message provided by the composite indicators in isolation can lead to simplistic conclusions, therefore, they are not a substitute for the partial indicators, but must be used in combination with them to obtain useful, informative and appropriate conclusions.

Composite indicators are increasingly used in very diverse areas; therefore, there are different approaches for its definition and construction. In practice, it is difficult to integrate individual indicators in a way that accurately reflects the reality to be monitored. The starting point should always be a thorough knowledge of the problem or concept to be addressed. The OECD statistical office produced a Handbook with a

listing of good practices that has become de facto the principal guide for designing, construction and use of composite indicators. The purpose of the Handbook is to provide builders and users of composite indicators with a set of recommendations on how to design, develop and disseminate composite indicators. In particular, the Handbook guides constructors and users by highlighting the technical problems and common pitfalls to be avoided (Joint Research Centre-European Commission, 2008).

Following the methodology proposed in the Handbook to build composite indicators, we will follow a process consisting of several steps. The first and most important stage to build composite indicator is the definition of the conceptual framework. It is the most important because it provides the basis for the other stages: it provides the basis for selecting variables, weights and methods of aggregation so that the synthetic index adequately reflects the structure of the phenomenon or reality to be analyzed. At the end, obtaining meaningful composite indicators for the objectives in the planning is a task that depends on the conceptual framework considered. If a dimension of the phenomenon to be analyzed is omitted at this stage, the composite indicator could lead to simplistic and/or erroneous conclusions. In our case, as in the initial stage of the process, the expert judgment has been used intensively through the Delphi to select the most relevant partial indicators, it is expected that the initial set of indicators would be adequate. Once the conceptual framework and the initial set of information have been determined, the most common situation is that the data present certain problems that may need to be addressed, such as missing data, atypical observations, etc.

Before we proceed to the weighting and aggregation of the individual indicators to construct the composite indicator, it is convenient to analyse the statistical structure of the database and compare the results with the theoretical conceptual framework in order to detect possible differences or similarities. Multivariate analysis can be useful to evaluate the suitability of the data set, since it is possible that the statistical similarity of the partial indicators can lead to a situation rich in indicators but poor in information. These techniques allow the identification of subgroups of individual indicators that are statistically 'similar'. In some situations, the results of this stage may imply rethinking of the construction of the synthetic index, having to go back to previous stages of the process.

Individual indicators will usually be expressed on a variety of scales; for that reason, the normalization of the dataset is a prior step previous to any type of aggregation of simple indicators; as usual, the standardization procedure should be consistent with the theoretical conceptual framework and statistical properties of the data, and robustness tests are necessary to evaluate their impact on the results.

Another important step in the process of constructing composite indicators is the weighting and aggregation of the various partial indicators. There are a variety of methods and procedures for selecting weights (DEA (data envelopment analysis), regression analysis, principal components, unobservable component models etc.), but one of the most used is weighted linear aggregation (Joint Research Centre-European Commission, 2008). Obviously, the theoretical framework and the properties of the data must be taken into account, and the final weights should reflect the relative importance of individual indicators in the construction of the particular composite indicator. We must be aware that regardless of the process and method used to choose the weights, in the end the weights represent value judgments that often respond and

show the objectives that are intended to be achieved with the construction of the composite indicator.

Once the weights corresponding to the different partial indicators are obtained, the aggregation method to be used must be determined. Again, we have that there exist different methods of aggregation. These can be classified into additive aggregation methods, geometric methods and multi-criteria aggregation methods. Before proceeding to the next step, the compatibility between the weighting methods and the aggregation methods should be analysed.

Finally, it is really convenient to undertake a statistical treatment to verify the robustness of the composite indicator to changes in the elements of the previous stages before completing the process of constructing a composite indicator and making it available to the final users.

4. Summary and concluding remarks

In this chapter, we have described and discussed a methodological procedure aimed at building an integrated information system for monitoring and evaluating public broadcasting corporations. The resulting information system encompasses data that reflects what public broadcasting corporations are like, what types of activities they do, what results they obtain from them, and what consequences all that generates for society as a whole. The procedure for elaborating the information system follows a conceptual framework based on organizational evaluation models, and consequently takes into account from the context within which corporations operate to the long-term consequences of their activity. To build up the information system we propose a two-stage operational procedure. The first stage consists of the selection, through expert judgment, of simple indicators that illustrate the most relevant aspects of the activities carried out by public broadcasting corporations. One or more catalogs of simple indicators suggested by international organizations provide the basis for the selection process. The second stage is the composition of a system of indicators specifically related to each relevant dimension and to each level of the hierarchy of objectives planned by the corporations in their respective strategic planning processes. The indicators are, in general, informative constructs that serve the strategies of the corporation. The strategy is the whole set of planned actions that, starting from a concrete reality with certain potentialities, and using human and material resources, are oriented to the achievement of a structured set of pre-established corporate objectives. That is, the strategy is a set of action patterns that relate the present, observed reality with a desire for a future reality through a planning of hierarchical objectives in the short and long term.

The system of indicators itself is designed at two levels. The first level is a basic indicator system, which includes the indicators that allow the description and monitoring of the reality of the activities of the corporations on a daily basis. These indicators refer to the environment and the context within which the diverse corporations may operate, their internal structure, the resources they command, the processes they undertake, the services and products they offer, and the results they

obtain with their activities. The basic indicator system provides the pieces of information needed to guide the ordinary management of corporate operations, and provides valuable knowledge base for future planning. The values of the basic indicators may be useful for defining typologies, or groupings of corporations with similarities in diverse aspects of interest for specific users; the resulting typologies would allow potential users to make reasonable comparisons of operational differences between corporations with similar characteristics. The second level of the system of indicators is the strategic indicator system, which should include indicators oriented to the planning, evaluation and benchmarking of the permanent operation of the broadcasting corporations. Strategic indicators express the consequences that the activities of a PBC generate in its environment, both in terms of its short-term effects and of its medium- and long-term impacts over the society that supports it. Strategic indicators are necessarily associated with planning and evaluation, and are oriented to support decision making at a level higher than that of ordinary operations management. An efficient way to monitor the progress towards the planned objectives is through appropriate sets of indicators. Therefore, the indicators mirror the objectives and these, in turn, can be of different types according to their hierarchical level in the planning of the PBC. In the planning process, the objectives follow an ascending hierarchy that classifies them into operational, specific, principal and strategic objectives. Thus, the indicators will have a different nature depending on the corresponding level of objectives whose degree of achievement we want to assess. The basic indicator system should contain indicators related to Context, Resources, Processes and Products, elements that correspond to the levels of operational and specific objectives. The Strategic System, in turn, should contain indicators related to Effects and Impacts, elements that correspond to the levels of main and strategic objectives, respectively. The basic system and the strategic system of indicators operate as two layers of the information system that guarantee that the whole system provides useful, reliable, consistent and appropriate information for decision-making about the reality of PBCs, at its different decision-making levels, and, consequently, oriented to the different stakeholders.

We understand the notion of an information system as the set of components that work together to collect, store and process data, and produce information in an organized, structured, adequate and valuable way for a variety of potential users. We believe that our proposal attempts to reduce the gap between traditional models of information-delivery systems and the natural process of the user when deciding to gather the data for a variety of potential uses. From this perspective, we propose to consider the information search process as a constructive activity of the final user to find meaningful information, and to give it a precise meaning within a personal or institutional frame of reference. In this sense, we highlight the fact that the efficiency of information-retrieval devices should take into account the integration of the results into the users' own work, as well as their evaluation of the usefulness of that information for problem solving and decision-making.

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